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Review Article

A Study On Barriers Towards Reporting Of Adverse Drug Reactions Among Healthcare Professionals

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ABSTRACT

Healthcare professionals play an important role in the establishment and functionality of Pharmacovigilance in a country. Hence, it is important to understand the barriers and facilitators that could have a significant impact on Healthcare professionals (HCPs) beliefs and practices. However, barriers that lead to the underreporting of ADRs exist in all healthcare systems. For the identification of barriers and development of interventions, theoretical domains framework has been extensively been used. It consists of domains covering the main factors influencing behaviour and barriers to behavioral change. This study aimed to identify the barriers to reporting ADRs among healthcare professionals. An observational study was conducted over a period of 6 months at Srinivas Institute of Medical Science & Research Centre, Mukka, Dakshina Kannada. A self-designed questionnaire was used to collect data on the barriers faced by 70 HCPs in reporting ADRs. From the data collected, it was revealed that majority of the Healthcare professionals were aware of what ADR was and had knowledge on ADR reporting system in India, but few of the nurses (6) lacked skills in reporting ADRs. Most of the HCPs (46) had fear of litigation, majority of HCPs complained lack of time and heavy workload as a major barrier to reporting ADRs. HCPs who were part of the study also informed there was active reporting of ADRs by the HCPs in the hospital and that there was no lack of team work. Based on the data collected it was found most of the HCPs were highly motivated and they had no problem in reporting of ADRs. In this study, lack of time, heavy workload, fear of litigation and punishment were identified as the main barriers to reporting ADRs among Healthcare professionals.

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INTRODUCTION

According to World Health Organization (WHO), an Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) is defined as “a response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for the prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modifications of physiological function.”[1] Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs), ranking as the fifth leading cause of mortality, contribute significantly to hospitalizations worldwide.[2] Healthcare professionals play an important role in the establishment and functionality of Pharmacovigilance in a country. Hence it is important to understand the barriers and facilitators, that could have a significant impact on Healthcare professionals’ beliefs and practices. However, in almost all healthcare systems barriers exist that lead to the underreporting of ADRs. Theoretical domains framework has extensively been used to identify barriers to ADRs reporting and also to develop interventions. It consists of domains covering the main factors influencing behaviour and barriers to behavioural change (Knowledge, Skills, Social influences etc.).[3] Identifying and reporting ADRs hold paramount importance, potentially aiding physicians in prescribing vigilantly and subsequently reducing healthcare costs. [4] Despite India's significant share of global medicine consumption, the reporting of ADRs only accounts for a mere 2% of the global incidence.[5] While India participates in the WHO's global ADR monitoring program relying on spontaneous reporting, its limited contribution stems from inadequate ADR reporting practices.[6] The system of spontaneous reporting has prompted the withdrawal of numerous marketed drugs due to safety concerns.[7] Presently, AMCs predominantly utilize a spontaneous reporting framework to relay instances of ADRs or AEs.[8] While healthcare improvement can transpire across various tiers of

the health system, a pivotal intervention involves supporting healthcare professionals in aligning their behaviors with evidence-based practices.[9] The specific behavior under evaluation for modification in this study pertains to the reporting of ADRs. A comprehensive comprehension of the impediments to this behavior marks an essential initial stride toward devising strategies capable of surmounting these barriers, thereby fostering effective interventions. This, in turn, enhances ADR reporting.[10] Enhanced theoretical insights into healthcare professionals' behaviors elevate the prospects of successful behavioral interventions. The application of theory facilitates grasping the factors and obstacles influencing the targeted behavioral shift, identifying potential techniques for altering clinical conduct, and elucidating the mechanics of these techniques.[11]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN:

The present work was an observational study that was conducted to identify barriers towards reporting of adverse drug reactions among healthcare professionals.

SAMPLE SIZE:

A total of 70 Healthcare Professionals working at Srinivas Institute of Medical Science & Research Centre, Mukka, Dakshina Kannada

ETHICAL CLEARANCE:

Ethical Clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Srinivas Institute of Medical Science and Research Centre (SIMS & RC), Mangalore.

STUDY CRITERIA:

Inclusion criteria:

- Healthcare professionals such as physicians, nurses and interns.

Exclusion criteria:

- Participants not willing to participate in the study.

SOURCE OF DATA:

The required information was collected from Healthcare professionals working at Srinivas Institute of Medical Science & Research Centre, Mukka, Dakshina Kannada, using a questionnaire to identify barriers and data obtained was analyzed.

MATERIALS USED:

A self-designed questionnaire was prepared and distributed among healthcare professionals (interns, nurses, physicians).

DATA ANALYSIS:

Statistical analysis involves collecting and scrutinizing every data sample in a set of items

from which samples can be drawn and a suitable statistical test was applied to analyze the data. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS 28.

RESULT

Demographic Characteristics

A total of 70 healthcare professionals participated in this study, providing a diverse range of insights. The participants were carefully selected to represent different roles within the healthcare sector, ensuring a well-rounded view of the topic at hand. Out of the 70 participants, 12 were physicians, 40 were MBBS and PHARM D interns, and 18 were nurses.

Figure 1: Healthcare Professionals involved

Table 1: Domains of identified barriers

Barriers Domain	Questions	Response	
		Yes	No
Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you define an ADR? Are you aware of ADR reporting system in India? 	67 (96%)	3 (4%)
Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have you ever reported an ADR? Are reporting forms complicated? 	64 (91%)	6 (9%)
Beliefs about consequences	Do you have fear of litigation in reporting ADR?	46 (66%)	24 (34%)
Social influences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are ADRs actively reported by other health professionals in your hospital? Do hospital managers and your colleagues approve your reported ADRs? Has there ever been lack of reporting due to unavailability of ADR reporting form 	70 (100%)	0
Motivation and Goals	Are you motivated to report ADRs?	45 (64%)	25 (36%)
Memory, attention, and decision process	Do you forget to report ADR that you encounter?	60 (86%)	10 (14%)
Heavy workload	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have you ever faced difficulty in 	55 (79%)	15 (21%)

	reporting ADR due to heavy workload?		
Lack of time	Do you think ADR reporting is time consuming?	50 (71%)	20 (29%)
Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you define an ADR? Are you aware of ADR reporting system in India? 	67 (96%)	3 (4%)
Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have you ever reported an ADR? Are reporting forms complicated? 	64 (91%)	6 (9%)
Beliefs about consequences	Do you have fear of litigation in reporting ADR?	46 (66%)	24 (34%)

In the category of “Knowledge” domain, the results revealed that 67 out of 70 healthcare professionals (96%) were aware of what ADR is and had knowledge on ADR reporting system in India. Lack of skills in reporting of ADRs were found in 6 out of 70 healthcare professionals (91%). The study results showed that, interns and physicians did know about procedure of reporting ADRs and found it easy. However, reporting ADRs was reported to be not easy by few of the nurses, due to lack of skills. In “Beliefs about consequences” domain, 46 of the healthcare professionals (66%) had fear of litigation and in the "environmental constraints" domain, 50 health care professionals (71%) complained lack of time and 55 of the healthcare professionals told heavy workload (79%) as a major barrier to reporting

ADRs. In “Social influences” domain all healthcare professionals participated in the informed that there was active reporting of ADRs by the healthcare professionals in the hospital and that there was sufficient team work between the healthcare professionals. No disapproval to reporting ADRs by hospital managers or by any other colleagues were reported by the participants. In "motivation and goals" domain, 45 healthcare professionals (64%) were highly motivated to report ADRs and reported that they never forget to report the suspected ADRs in the hospital. In "memory, attention and decision process" domain, 60 healthcare professionals (86%) informed that they had never forgotten to report suspected ADRs.

Figure 2: Barriers identified in ADR Reporting

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that nurses, interns, and physicians in the hospital demonstrated a good understanding of what Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) are, as well as a comprehensive grasp of the ADR reporting system in India. This indicates that the medical staff is well-informed about the definitions and protocols associated with ADRs. In the "Skills" domain, the study found that both interns and physicians exhibited a high level of proficiency in reporting ADRs, considering the process to be straightforward and manageable. This suggests that these groups are well-equipped to handle ADR reporting efficiently as part of their routine practice. However, the study identified that some nurses encountered challenges in reporting ADRs due to skill deficiencies. This highlights a gap in training or experience among certain nursing staff, which may hinder the effectiveness of ADR reporting within the hospital setting. These findings are consistent with the results of a study conducted by Cheema E et al., [12] In the domains of "Beliefs about Consequences," "Lack of Time," and "Heavy Workload," the study identified key barriers that hinder the reporting of

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) in the hospital setting. One of the major barriers noted was the fear of punishment and litigation, which discourages healthcare professionals from reporting ADRs. This fear is rooted in concerns about potential repercussions, including disciplinary action or legal consequences that might arise from acknowledging an ADR. Additionally, the study highlighted that a lack of time and increased workloads are significant obstacles to effective ADR reporting. Healthcare professionals often find themselves overwhelmed with their regular duties, leaving them with insufficient time to properly document and report ADRs. The heavy workload further exacerbates this issue, as the demands of patient care take precedence, pushing the task of ADR reporting to a lower priority. These findings align with those of a study conducted by Mirbaha F et al., which also identified fear of punishment and litigation, lack of time, and heavy workloads as primary challenges to ADR reporting among healthcare professionals. [11] In the "Social Influences" domain, the study observed that healthcare professionals in the hospital are actively engaged in reporting Adverse

Drug Reactions (ADRs). There was no indication of a lack of teamwork or disapproval from hospital managers or colleagues regarding ADR reporting. This suggests a positive and supportive social environment where ADR reporting is encouraged and valued, fostering collaboration among staff and endorsement from management. On the other hand, in the "Motivation and Goals" domain, the study found that healthcare professionals were highly motivated to report suspected ADRs. Their strong commitment to patient safety and adherence to reporting protocols was evident. This high level of motivation indicates that healthcare professionals understand the importance of ADR reporting and are driven to contribute to the pharmacovigilance process. In the "Memory, Attention, and Decision Process" domain, the study revealed that most healthcare professionals consistently remembered to report ADR cases. This consistent recollection and attention to detail highlight their dedication to maintaining accurate and timely ADR reports, ensuring that no cases are overlooked. These findings contrast with those of the study conducted by Mirbaha F et al. which reported issues related to social influences, motivation and memory, namely, challenges in team dynamics, managerial support, and the personal motivation and memory of healthcare staff, which negatively impacted ADR reporting practices. [11]

CONCLUSION

The important barriers assessed by the study were related to seven domains of Knowledge, Skills, beliefs about consequences, Motivation and goals, Environmental constraints, Social influences and Memory, attention and decision process. In this study, lack of time, Heavy workload, fear of litigation and punishment were identified as the chief barriers to ADR reporting ADRs. To overcome these barriers a comprehensive intervention should include time management training, strategies such as revising and shortening

of reporting procedures and also to provide help in reporting of ADRs. To overcome fear of litigation and punishment we found that there is a need to educate healthcare professionals. Analysis of the study results indicates barriers to reporting highlights areas for focused effort Overall, this study provides a foundation for future initiatives aimed at enhancing ADR reporting practices, ultimately contributing to the goal of safeguarding patients' well-being and reducing healthcare costs.

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